

SEMANTICS OF CATTLE-RELATED ETHNOGRAPHIES ANALYSIS

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ANNOTATION.

The article provides brief information on the analysis of Uzbek animal husbandry ethnographies, as well as their research. In particular, on the basis of the fact that the ethnographic lexicon of the Uzbek language has not been fully studied on a regional basis, the researches related to cattle breeding of the Surkhan oasis were studied. Linguistic, cultural, economic, political analysis processes were studied. Food ethnographies related to animal husbandry, ethnographies related to livestock and their members, ethnographic traditions related to animal husbandry were briefly discussed.

KEY WORDS: Ethnolexems, semantics of ethnographisms, livestock terms, herders' speech, hunting ethnographies.

INTRODUCTION. VALIDITY OF THE SUBJECT

The ethnographic lexicon of the Uzbek language has not been fully studied on a regional basis, and this situation also applies to the regional dialects that we are studying. A complete study of this problem will help to reveal some aspects of the history of the people and the language that are still abstract. Due to the fact that representatives of different nationalities lived in this region, their languages have unique aspects, which is also visible in their ethnographic lexicon.

It is known that Uzbeks are one of the nations with the oldest cultural traditions in the world. The roots of the masterpieces of material and spiritual culture, created and polished by our people over the centuries, go back to very distant times. The analysis of the semantic nature of the livestock ethnography of the Surkhandarya oasis serves as a scientific-theoretical basis for the study of ethnography as a language and a national spiritual unit, ethnolinguistics, linguo-culturology, general linguistics, etc. It is based on the fact that science textbooks are an important source for the creation of study guides.

Review of scientific literature on the topic.

"Unfortunately, our modern Uzbek literary language," writes Bosim Toychiev, "has left out many words related to livestock such as pasture, village, otov, keraga." Just as a big barrier has been placed between our modern literary language and our classical language, such barriers have been made very imperceptible between the literary language and the language of the common people and the language of examples of folk art. As a result, our literary language has lost most of them." Also, the author attributes the current Uzbek literary language to three sources: 1) classical language; 2) universal language; 3) he rightly stated that folk oral creativity should rely on the language of riddles, proverbs, phrases, fairy tales and epics.¹

Dialectologist scientist B. Joraev said that it is impossible to determine the norms of our literary language without studying the language of folklore texts, which preserve not only dialects, but also ethnographic traditions.²

It was emphasized that it is of scientific and practical importance to start studying the lexical layer of Tilnin, its speech features, linguopoetics, including euphemisms, first of all, by researching the speech of herders. After all, the history of the problem is that livestock breeding was the basis for the formation of all professional fields or had a direct and indirect influence. This is T. Tursunova also rightly stated that livestock (cattle and its products) was the basis for the formation and development of professional occupations such as weaving, carpet making, goldsmithing, mahsi and kavshdozh.³

O.T. Orinova and T. Orinov also say that cattle breeding is the most ancient form of social economy of the people of Uzbekistan and Central Asia in general, and livestock lexicon is the oldest developed layer of the Uzbek language, that is, they (cattle lexicon) are names of people (anthroponyms), places They said that they played an important role in the development of the system of names (toponyms), cosmic

¹ Toychiev B. Formation of the words yailov, kishlov, keraga and gold // Uzbek language and literature, 2000, No. 3, – B. 68.

² Joraev B. Upper Kashkadarya Uzbek dialects. - T.: Science, 1969. - B. 80-81.

³ Tursunova T. From the history of carpet making lexicon in Uzbek language. "Scientific works" of ToshDPI named after Nizami, volume 87. - B. 3-17; this author. Lexicon of applied arts of the Uzbek language. - T. Science, 1978.

bodies (astroponyms), names of divine concepts (theonyms), clan names (ethnonyms), and these should be studied in a broad plan.⁴

DISCUSSIONS

Ethnographies related to animal husbandry can be divided into the following subgroups ethnographic lexicon; worm, suzgi, kelagay, cream, ayron, tandir meat, stew, hard cream, palla, chakki, belly meat, fry, kogan, kapa, kilyk, gupi, toshayil, uzangi, komma;

- ethnographies representing the names of livestock and their members: ram, taka, goat, shishak, chori, mangi, panji, chibich, tuvcha, gunanjin, baytal, tay, kurra, hooves, ashik;

- ethnographic traditions related to animal husbandry; to ent, put horses and rams, enchi, joyuv, chagana, queue, rest, bring out abruk, give blessing, dangana, finish the goods, reap, uyaz, jaylov, uyur, take heels, swallow heels, homtalash;

- ethnographies related to hunting: tent, jela, nail, putta, putta putta, basket, tapaka; - ethnographies related to crafts: zhuvov, talkoshikh, urchik, tash, chiy, ergana, adip, arqov, juntarak.

Ethnolexems representing spiritual culture include the language, oral and written literature, art, music, traditional medicine, faith, religious, moral traditions and mentality of the ethnos. The ethnographies belonging to this thematic group are diverse in terms of their semantics, and have hardly been studied in Uzbek linguistics.

Ethnolexems representing national cultural meaning in the lexical layer of the language allow analysis of ethnic, linguistic, cultural, social, economic, and political aspects shared between brotherly peoples and nations in general.

It is known that the etymological meaning of the word cattle is Persian: chor+po⁵ – four-legged, four-legged; and the word herdsman has four legs (-dor is from the Persian word dori, which means to have, owner), a person who has four legs, i.e. cattle.

⁴ Orinova O.T., Orinov T. Livestock lexicon and Uzbek onomastics // Onomastics of Uzbekistan. - T.: 1989. - B. 176-178.

⁵ Aidarav T. Arealnaya characteristicsika dialectknoy lexike kazakhskih govorov Uzbekistana. Autoref. diss... cand. Philol. Nauk. - Alma-Ata, 1980. - B. 37-42.

The meaning of livestock was later expanded and became essential, animal ⁶(Arabic: living, life), wealth (Arabic: state, wealth), and the person who keeps livestock was called a shepherd (Persian: shab+bon - keeper of the night).

First of all, the ethnography of livestock, the names and terms of livestock, such as the type of animal (such as camel, horse, ox, donkey, sheep, goat, pig, deer, rabbit); gender (male, female, nar-modra (nar-modra is mostly used for birds); lok, nor, moya, camel; stallion, horse, biya, baytal; ox, bull, cow, heifer; hangi, mocha, moda; ram, cold; taka, sarka, goat; boar, pig, megajin; quralay, ghazal, ghazal); age (bush, mare, camel; kulon, mare, gunon, dunon, horse; calf, body, juvona, ox; lamb, Sangach, tokhli, tusok (dusog'), dagar, shishak, chori, panji, hangi, mangi; goat, goat, chibich, tutcha, goat⁷; It is impossible to study its taboos and euphemisms without knowing the terms related to it (such as churpi, torpi, torray, pig).

In this place, the owners of a profession, for example, cattle breeders, in their speech use sheep running, tol, tola, choroyna, uvuz (mouth), bochalamak, palla, kelagay, suzgi, konargi, tomizgi, uyutma, whiteness, kortmak, akyramk, yydirma, enchi, chagana. hundreds of words such as , ogaliq, koshank, kokan, kuvi (kubi), tulup, pishgak, koton, kora, enlanmak, bichmiq, akhtalamak, sangach, tuvcha, tokhli, shishak, dagar, chibich, chuv, kohak, wake up, run away, stop , use phrases and expressions that raise the question of whether this speech can be called a professional speech. In our opinion, it is necessary to recognize that the word professional has two interrelated phases: narrow and broad concepts. In the first case, professionals use professional lexical tools that others cannot use. Speech acquires professionalism (professional behavior).

⁶ Nishonova N. Meaningful analysis of the field of lexemes with archiseme "animal" in the Uzbek language. Philol.fanl.nomz. ... diss. autoref. - T., 2000.

⁷ Fayzieva Kh. Boysun-Shor'chi naming of nouns according to age, color, gender in Uzbek dialects // Current issues of linguistics and problems of speech culture (Proceedings of the conference of the Republic). - Termiz, 2004. - B. 81-84; Kabilov E. What do we know about the horse // Dialogue, No. 3, 2002. – B. 46-47.

Ethnography appears and is formed in connection with the way of life of livestock: birth, feeding, calving, reproduction, number (amount), production, disease, death, character, role in human life.

- Ethnography related to animal names and characteristics. Dog. Since the dog played a major role in the life of man, especially the herdsman, he received the term faithful ethnography. For example, the dog is barking, if it is a simple bark, someone has come; if it barks in parts (especially in the steppe), there is a predator; if it hisses, there is a snake in a bush; if he scratches the ground and barks, a strange dog has come; even if it is tied, if the husband scratches and rubs it, it will come loose. The dog, sniffing and moving quickly, found a trace of something; depending on the situation: there is a spy or blackmailer. A dog howling is a sad event, it can even be a death.

Saying the word "dog" is sometimes called "vafador" because it is taboo: Sarban answered "Vafodor" to Sarayban's question: "Vafodor" (M., "Me'mor", p. 26).

Wolf. In different places, the wolf is called by euphemistic names such as: aqquluq, koktaka, jandor, kabishqir (in the sense of closing the jaw), karishqul, itqush, black, "owner" (kesatiq), situation, that is, the wolf has come to the sheep, the wolf is talking, the dogs are barking loudly, the dogs are seeing black, turning black, turning lively, the sheep are barking, restless, and sparkling; a wolf came to the herd, he was wandering, a living creature came to the herd, a living creature ran, a living creature wandered; The concept of the wolf ate the sheep, the wolf took the sheep is understood through EVs such as the gajir is spinning, the gajir is being thrown, or emtigi (remains of livestock after the wolf has eaten them - remains) is found. The sheep we were looking for fell into the hands of the "owner" (from "Boysun tong") euphemism: a) wolf ate; b) is used in the sense of a thief stole. This year the blue buck increased in Bobotog, took five cattle in one night (from the shepherd's mouth).

A convenient low place where a wolf can come is called chobit. Take the wolf, be careful of the wolf, is a euphemism for the concepts of don't let the wolf come, block the way the wolf comes.

It is known that the movement of livestock is controlled by a person: a lying animal is raised, driven, moved, stopped, fed, used, watered, harvested, ridden and so

on. There are certain "communication" tools and their euphemisms used for these processes. For example, when a quiet animal is driven from a pen or pen (when it is agitated, especially at night), it is usually not yelling, pointing a stick, and pushing, but all kinds of high-low, thin, soft, musical euphemistic whistles (which cannot be expressed in writing)), chu, guv, chuh, hush, husht, hayt, soft, low-pitched signals (exclamations) such as chu, guv, chuh, hush, husht, hayt, or are set in motion by stirring and raising the sark.

If there is a problem in managing or returning the goods to a certain direction - double; if it's a goat - cha, chig, chigi; if it is an ox, it is called a head. In other words, it is unnatural and funny to say to a sheep - cha, to a goat - double, to an ox, to a cow - chigi, double. For example:

I raised goats

I started yesterday

Dates have milk,

I don't want to go

In the couplet "There's a dog in love" (from the song of the shepherd in love), chachalab is used in connection with the movement of the goat.

The exclamations chu, chuv, chuh are used when driving a horse, ox, or cow. When stopping a horse, dirr, turr, turr, tak, tak, tak-tak, tak-tak, all kinds of rhythmic signals that cannot be expressed through graphic means are used. When calling a horse or sheep at a certain distance, go, go, go! tuff-hey, tuff-hey! Calling the goat-goat! come out! (accent is long on the last syllable), moo-moo, mooh-mooh, hoovv-hoovv, or a soft, low-pitched whistle (not expressed in writing) is used when the horse is being watered. When the camel is drowning, it is squealing, squealing; xix in moving ass! hi! ix!, ushsh, ushsh, yushsh when stopping; callousness; when calling a dog by means of a baah or a whistle, when driving stand, go, stand, when directing at a predator or an enemy, take, kish, take-kish, when calling a puppy, kut-kut (from which kut-kut), kut-kut-kut (in which there is a gentle tone that descends from above), chip, chip EVs are used in driving.

In addition, the animal world communicates with humans through euphonic sounds, flute, sybizg (sybyzik, sybyzdik), and drums. is evidence.

- Ethnographies related to cattle herding. To denote the animal's readiness to mate and its desire to mate, kuikibdi (general concept), agirtalab (biya, baytal), buqatalab (cow), hangitalab (mocha), takatalab (goat), kochkortalab (sovliq) became; iliqibdi (dog), mov became (cat) – (concrete concept); in relation to the concept of mating, intercourse, stallion, bull, ram, foal; The euphemisms "stopped-didn't-stopped" and "didn't run away" are used for the concept (strait) related to the result of mating. The term sheep breeding (a special place for artificial insemination of sheep) is also related to this concept.

In place of the word tugmuq, the euphemism tul tânlik ⁸(tul means to fill up, increase) is used in the speech of Turkic herdsmen. . Don't let the owner do less. Sheep and goats are in full bloom, there are many twins, and there are even triplets (if three lambs or goats are born, they are called triplets) (K. Kholmo'minov, "One Day of Koklam", p. 4).

- Ethnographies related to the amount of livestock. Usually, the cattle owner or shepherd counts the cattle at a certain time (often once a day) in order to know whether the cattle are there or not. This is called "stock completion" in the herdsman's speech. Since it is taboo to openly say the amount of goods, even counting is done secretly (inside); if there is no need, the result is not stated: everything is in place - complete; a few use incomplete euphemisms instead of no. So the concepts of yes and no are taboo to a certain extent.

Has the milker milked all her cattle? Any un milked cattle left? not with the words "yes", "no" or "no", but "rich" (from the verb to become rich), How much do you have? or how many when asked clearly: with an abstract number, yes, thank God, there are four or five or fifteen or twenty. Even in many cases, the names of livestock species are not mentioned: ox, cow, body, calf, etc. - cattle, black, big, big horned; sheep, lamb, goat, goat, sarka, taka etc. are euphemized with terms such as small, small, small.

⁸ Budagov L. Sravnitelnyy slovar turetsko-tatarskikh narechiy. - t. I – II, SPb. - B. 1868-1871.

- Ethnographies related to cattle bones and their parts. In this case, words like love, rib, femur, bone marrow, ankle, etc., besides their real meanings, come in figurative meanings and are attributed to human actions and activities and have acquired a euphemistic meaning. For example, instead of saying that "so-and-so" was lucky, lucky, lucky, and his work went well, the euphemism is used to avoid the evil eye, evil eye, and enemies: Kadyrov's lover is half a hat of cherry.

His rib is visible and his ribs can be counted is a euphemistic expression of the concept that he is skinny, cannot be slaughtered, and cannot be eaten. The expressions "I don't like my rib" and "My rib doesn't match my rib" are euphemistic expressions of dislike, disagreement on some issue, for example, trade: I don't think your horse is bad, I want to buy it, but our rib doesn't match our rib ("Chaganiyon", 2000, May 3).

Did the horn (-ng, -im) come out? the rhetorical interrogative is a euphemistic expression of the "goal" and unpleasant reality created by a false, forced, illegal act: Grandfather Askar asked the neighbor boy (regretting that he left his family and married another woman): Has your horn come out? (M. Safarov) .

Also, the knife cut to the bone in work means to be fed up, to be full of patience, to attack, to be ready for a tragic reality; Fathers take heart from the wedding, fatherless people look around (from the herdsman's speech), their speech is annoying, those who have a back (support), officials are always in honor and respect; foreigners live in exile and humiliation; The marrow is full, the marrow is strong - strong, rich, rich; The ethnographies of the concepts of a person with a dry marrow, a weak marrow, a weak person, and a poor person were discussed.

CONCLUSION

Due to its high artistic potential, our people, who have created invaluable examples of folk art since ancient times, are creators of folklore traditions and ceremonial values that played an important role in the development of the culture of not only Central Asia, but also the peoples of the East. The national traditions of the Uzbek people have been passed down from generation to generation and improved because our ancestors enriched and further developed the priceless national folklore traditions created by their forefathers with the product of their artistic thinking. After

all, the ancient roots of the artistic thinking of our ancestors go back to such distant times that the folklore works, which have been popularized by the people for thousands of years, have been enriched and enriched by eloquent performers, are considered to be the roots of our national values.

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